

FERGHANA MEDICAL COMMUNITY AND PUBLIC HEALTH ISSUES

¹Egamnazarov A.I., ²Imamnazarova D.A.

¹Senior teacher of the department "Social Sciences" of Fergana Public Health Medical Institute

²6th-course student of the Faculty of Treatment of Fergana Public Health Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13890901>

Abstract. *In this article, on the basis of historical and scientific sources, the activities of foreign health professionals of Fergana Medical Community, which was established in the Fergana Valley in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, are studied.*

Keywords: *Fergana Medical Community, infectious diseases, vaccination, hygiene, prevention, healing water, treatment with water.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest the relevance of the topic, where public health protection is one of the important issues that need to be addressed in the social sphere during the formation of new Uzbekistan. The reforms implemented in the field of medicine during the development of our country pay special attention to the role and significance of foreign specialists in the training of qualified medical personnel, based on this, it is important to study how this issue was implemented in our country in the late 19th - early 20th centuries. For this purpose, in this article we tried to cover such issues as the role and place of foreign (German) medical specialists in solving public health problems in Central Asia, in particular, in Fergana Valley, and their impact on the socio-economic life of the country.

Level of study of the problem. It is known to everyone, that many scholars like Rakhimov M., Matveyev A.M., Khonkeldiev Yu. made significant studies regarding the topic. In their works, not only the fight against various infectious diseases, the opening of hospitals and pharmacies, vaccination and improvement of urban and rural sanitation, but also the creation of Scientific Centers, scientific articles, lectures and seminars on the study of the causes of diseases in the life of the valley and their treatment were studied. We also relied on archival documents, precise data, figures and opinions of a number of authors about the activities of foreign specialists in the medical field in Fergana Valley.

The purpose of the study. How the activities of foreign medical specialists were organized in our country in the late 19th - early 20th centuries, the influence of the activities of foreign (German) doctors on the social and spiritual life of Central Asia, especially in Fergana region have been covered.

Research methodology. The given article presents the relationship between medical consciousness and medical culture using historical, economic, logical principles, a deterministic approach and a discourse analysis method.

Research results. In the development strategy of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the issue of health care in the social sphere. Health care is considered one of the most important areas of human health in society, and Fergana Medical Community has successfully begun work on this issue in the valley since 1897. The community had 50 members and carried out prevention and other preventive measures against infectious diseases among the population. In particular, lectures on topical issues of medicine of that time were given by general practitioners Aberburg A.K., Ortenberg P.I., Geyshtor M.A. and dozens of other members of the community. At public

meetings, doctors took part with their lectures including Shlamm O.M. "On the Impact of the Broken Air on the Pamir Heights", doctor Fegler G.G. "Kilegeniya Erysipelas", doctor Birkina N.D. "Composition of the Population of Kokand Mokhauzar (Leprosarium)", doctor Braunstein A.M. "On the Bubonic Plague", doctor Braunstein A.M. "Siberian Measles", doctor Meisels "A Case of Natural Smallpox", doctor Mali A.V. "On Anthrax", doctor Gimbutt B.D. "Two Cases of the Use of Antidiphtheria Serum in Diphtheria of the Pharynx" and others. The reports were discussed by the members of the community and the necessary measures were determined. The text of these lectures is currently stored in the library of the regional health department.

Besides that, Geyshtor Maria Aleksandrovna (1859-1936), a member of the community, began her medical career in Fergana region in 1889. She used all her knowledge and experience to maintain the health of valley's residents. For her services in eliminating the cholera epidemic in 1892, she was awarded the "Gold Medal".

It is important to suggest that on September 30, 1886, the Turkestan Governor-General signed the Regulation on new city hospitals. It is known that earlier, like other specialists who came to Turkestan from Russia and other countries, doctors, physicians and paramedics provided medical services in private hospitals.

By the end of the 19th century, medical institutions began to open in the cities of Turkestan, including a military hospital for 50 people in New Margilon, the first hospital in the city with 35 beds for 20 men and 15 women in 1886. A free eye hospital in 1901 [1].

On September 12, 1887, Turkestan Governor-General von K.P. Kaufman gave permission to open an outpatient clinic for women and children in Andijan. The outpatient clinic began its work on February 8, 1888, under the direction of Olimpiya Solnyshkina [2].

Definitely, the clinic, located in the city center, employed only female paramedics. After the establishment of the institution, a large number of sick women and children began to seek treatment there. From February 8 to August 1 of the year, the institution's staff provided medical care to 1,339 women and 640 children and 4,290 patients at home [3].

In 1896, the number of medical personnel in Fergana region was 68 people: 1 regional, 5 district, 4 city, 4 female doctors, 22 paramedics, 4 paramedics, 21 anti-epidemic vaccinators and 7 sanitary workers, of whom 9 were German citizens. In 1890, there was a 5-bed treatment center, 1 outpatient clinic, and 1 pharmacy in Margilon district; by 1913, there was a 15-bed hospital, 1 pharmacy, where 2 doctors, 4 paramedics, and 2 pharmacists served patients [4].

It is known from history that chickenpox took the lives of hundreds of people. That is why this issue was especially emphasized in the Regulations on the Turkestan Administration, and the duties of district and city doctors were defined. According to the charter, they were not limited to treating patients among the population, but were also required to vaccinate against smallpox and train apprentice assistants from the local population for this work. In 1909, 1,228 children were vaccinated in the city of Andijan, and 6,856 in the district [5].

Moreover, nearly 1913 even 1995 children in the city and 9,073 in the district were vaccinated against chickenpox. A major role in this vaccination campaign was played by the services of Elizabeth and Hermann Gross, a family of German doctors who came to Andijan. Dr. Pipper R.A. was the head of plague treatment in Andijan in 1896 [6].

In March 1914, the first maternity hospital opened in Skobelev. As the population grew, so did the number of medical workers, and in 1913 their number in the city was 5 highly educated doctors (1 woman), 7 paramedics (2 women), 1 dentist, 2 surgeons and 2 pharmacists. 2 private

pharmacies - began operating in 1886 and 1899. In 1900, 2 state pharmacies were created [7]. Among the medical staff, 2 female doctors and 2 nurses were Germans by nationality.

In addition, the head of the city outpatient clinic, chief physician G.G. Fegler, chief sanitary doctor K.O. Reingart, head of the city pharmacy K.B. were responsible for maintaining public health, the sanitary condition of cities and villages, drinking water and water supply, preventing the spread of various infectious diseases, conscientiously fulfilling their professional and universal duties in receiving [8].

In addition to treating patients, doctors also monitored the sanitary condition of the city. The police, together with the sanitary commission, monitored cleanliness. Of the 5 toilets built for personal hygiene, 4 were for Russians and 1 for Uzbeks [9]. Doctors also saved people from various infectious and dangerous diseases. They worked hard to preserve the health of the local population within their capabilities. Especially in 1910, when the plague spread in Andijan, by order of Fergana governor, the doctors in Asht, Isfara, Bozorkurgan district, the paramedics in Rishton, Shakhrikhan, Chimyon district were involved in the fight against this disease. At the suggestion of doctors, several mobile pharmacies were organized to fight this infectious disease and German doctors Elizaveta and Hermann Gross, A.G. Vilman and M.G. Rotler showed particular activity in the fight against this catastrophe. Total expenditure on health care in 1892 amounted to 2921 rubles [10].

On February 9, 1901, the chief physician of the region wrote to the Fergana governor that the number of people seeking medical care in Andijan, Kokan, Margilon and Namangan districts of the region was increasing from year to year. That is why it was proposed to allocate 1000 rubles for the purchase of medicines instead of 400 rubles and 180 rubles for the acquisition of medical equipment. [11]

However, there were also specific problems in this area. Compared to the country's population, the number of existing hospitals, outpatient clinics, doctors and medical personnel was very small and could not meet the needs of the valley. In 1900, in Andijan, one male and one female doctor served 49,682 people and in Andijan district, one doctor served 319,951 people, or one doctor per 16,080 square meters of territory [12]. In one pharmacy in Old Margilan, there was a hospital with 15 beds, a hospital for women and children with 10 beds, 2 doctors, 4 paramedics and 2 pharmacists. In 1913 more than 15,632 rubles were allocated from the city budget for health and sanatorium-resort work, and 480 rubles per year for public education. However, 28,271 rubles were spent from the city budget on the maintenance of 53 police officers [13].

Most people are not familiar with Hazrat Ayub station near Jalalabad in Fergana region (now Jalalabad sanatorium), there is healing water for human health. In 1879, German chemist Hermann Terek, who came to Fergana, examined the water content and gave preliminary conclusions. But 6 years later, a group of doctors - Piper, Shapiro, master Verblüner - were sent to check the composition of Hazrat Ayub water. Even after the studies turned out to be very effective, the tsarist officials treated them coolly. However, in the medical report of the doctors it was shown that this healing water can treat gastrointestinal diseases. Nevertheless, this issue was considered from under the paws, and finally in 1899, the Main Military Medical Inspectorate under the Governor-General of Turkestan recognized that the water was of national importance and sent inspector Hermann Tereks to conduct a more in-depth study of the water composition and install a purification system. The study yielded better results than expected. The German scientist's observations aimed at studying the composition of water were not in vain. The physical and

chemical properties of water were determined and it was established that one cubic meter of open water contains 0.053 grams of iodine, as well as calcium, magnesium, sulfuric acid, sodium, calcium, potassium chloride and other minerals. It was established that the released gas consists of carbon dioxide and atmospheric air [14].

Jalalabad is also famous for its numerous mineral healing springs. The fame of these healing waters, founded by German scientists, has spread not only to Fergana Valley, but also far beyond its borders. Near several healing hot mineral springs at an altitude of 981 meters above sea level, there are world-class balneological resorts where people come suffering from diseases of the hands, feet, nervous system, liver, bile ducts, kidneys, as well as gynecological and skin diseases are treated.

The wonderful mountain climate, the abundance of trees and sunlight, as well as the beautiful landscapes of Kugars River attract people. Due to this, Jalalabad and the adjacent lands are a favorite vacation spot for Fergana residents. Even now, thousands of people from all over the world come to these sanatoriums for treatment.

Dozens of such healing mineral waters in Fergana Valley serve human health. For example: 8 health resort hospitals in Chimyon treat rheumatism from back, leg and arm pain. Children's sanatorium located on a mountain in Shakhimardan treats pulmonary diseases, 3 sanatoriums in Ropkan (Besharik district) treat gallstone disease, pancreas and other diseases with mud and water. In Kyzyltepe (Altyarik district) there are 5 sanatoriums, from where healing water flows naturally with the same temperature of 38 degrees throughout the year, the water contains about 20 minerals that effectively support human health. In the sanatoriums of Chust, Chortok (Namangan region), a method of water treatment has been introduced that promotes the work of the nerves and blood vessels of the heart. The sanatoriums of Shakhrikhan, Izboskan, Pakhtaabad (Andijan region) also serve to strengthen the health of our people. From historical sources it is known that these healing waters were studied by German specialists 100-120 years ago.

Fergana Valley has the above and even more unique aspects such as weather, climate, nature, orchards, hardworking people, art, architecture, artisans and carpenters, which have interested scientists since ancient times.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that the area studied by the authors shows that in the medicine of Fergana Valley there are great opportunities for the treatment and prevention of various diseases. In deepening reforms in medicine in the modern period, scientific and practical work carried out by foreign specialists will be of great importance for the effective implementation of medical reforms in our country today.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimov M. History of Fergana, T., "Fan", 1984, P. 16.
2. "Turkistani News" September 15, 1887.
3. The past, present and future of the city of Margilon. Fergana, 2007, P.56.
4. Statistical review of the Fergana region for 1909. Skobel. 1911. P. 92
5. Statistical review of the Fergana region for 1913, P.108.
6. Rakhimov M. History of Fergana, T., "Fan", 1984, P. 17.
7. Matveyev. A. M. On the issue of people from Germany in Central Asia in the late 19th -early 20th centuries. "Scientific Works". TashGU, issue 392, Tashkent, 1970. P. 64.
8. Rakhimov M. History of Fergana. P. 17.

9. Review of the Fergana Region for 1892, Novy Margilan, 1893, P. 81, 57.
10. TsGA.UzSSR.f.i.19.op 1,d 32651.l.P.18-21.
11. Stat.review.Ferg.region for 1908 Skobelev, 1910. P. 164.
12. Khonkeldiev Yu. Margilan. T., "Uzbekistan", 1968. P. 11.
13. Yearbook of the Fergana region 1902. T.oi 1. New Margilan. Printing house of the Fergana regional manifestation. P. 72-73.
14. Matveyev A.M. From the history of Asian and European immigrants in Central Asia at the beginning of the twentieth century. "Scientific works of Tashkent State University" issue 423. Tashkent, 1972. P. 72-73.
15. Egamnazarov Azamjon Imamnazarovich, Mamadaliev Nemat Kahorovich. The role of german entrepreneurs in the development of entrepreneurship and banking in the Ferghana valley. Science and innovation international- scientific journal volume 2 issue 4 April 2023, P.101-106